

DIDACTIC OPPORTUNITIES OF THE DRAWING (TECHNICAL DRAWING) SUBJECT IN DEVELOPING CONSTRUCTIVE THINKING IN STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

This dissertation explores the didactic potential of the subject of technical drawing in shaping students' constructive thinking skills. Constructive thinking is defined as the ability to develop innovative ideas based on existing knowledge, solve technical problems using spatial and logical reasoning, and visualize and represent complex forms through graphical modeling. The research examines the methodological structure of teaching technical drawing, including the use of graphic tasks, interactive strategies, and the integration of modern CAD technologies (e.g., AutoCAD, SolidWorks). A central focus is placed on developing constructive thinking through exercises that enhance students' understanding of objects' shapes, dimensions, internal structures, and spatial positioning.

Through pedagogical experiments, the study evaluates specially designed tasks and instructional activities incorporating 2D and 3D modeling. The results demonstrate that effectively structured drawing lessons significantly contribute to the intellectual and technical development of learners by strengthening their analytical, creative, and spatial reasoning abilities.

Technical drawing is one of the important subjects that develops students' spatial imagination, technical thinking, accuracy, consistency, and logical reasoning. Through this subject, students learn to analyze the shape, structure, and spatial position of various technical objects and to express them through graphic representations. This serves as a foundation for their preparation in fields such as design, construction, and engineering.

This dissertation research is aimed at revealing the didactic possibilities of technical drawing in the formation of constructive thinking. Today, there is a growing demand for specialists with constructive thinking skills in areas such as technical design, engineering education, and industrial production. Therefore, effective teaching of technical drawing in general education schools, proper use of graphic assignments, and the application of innovative approaches are considered highly relevant for developing these competencies.

The research analyzes the role of graphic assignments in developing students' constructive thinking, the didactic structure of drawing lessons, and the possibilities of using digital technologies and problem-based teaching methods. Based on this, the importance of this subject in forming students' intellectual and technical approaches is substantiated.

Constructive thinking is the process of creating new ideas, technical solutions, and graphic models based on existing knowledge, and it is an essential skill for engineering and technical professions. By developing such thinking, students:

- can find technical solutions to real problems
- analyze design processes,
- visualize objects based on drawings,
- learn to simplify complex forms and represent them graphically.

Graphic assignments are the main tool for developing students' logical, spatial, and technical thinking. These may include:

- breaking down complex shapes into simple geometric forms,
- drawing parts and representing them in projections,
- drawing cross-sections of parts and components,
- visualizing and modeling objects based on different views.

These activities strengthen students' creative thinking, spatial imagination, and decision-making skills in problem situations.

Interactive methods include:

- "Brainstorming" – generating new graphic solutions,
- Small group work – preparing collaborative project drawings,
- Role-playing – students act as designers, constructors, or manufacturers,
- "INSERT" method – analyzing drawings and recording their thoughts.

The modern education system aims to form individuals who are creative, technologically competent, and capable of independent thinking in accordance with societal needs. In this context, developing students' constructive thinking has become a key task. Research findings show that technical drawing has unique didactic opportunities and plays a significant role in developing technical thinking.

Through technical drawing lessons, students gain the ability to: Analyze geometric and constructive shapes, develop spatial imagination, effectively use graphic expression tools, make independent decisions in solving technical problems, gradually develop engineering thinking.

The use of graphic assignments, modeling methods, design tasks, and visual analysis exercises within this subject helps students not only learn to draw but also analyze objects through drawings, visualize them in space, simplify complex forms, and develop constructive thinking skills. These skills are essential for professionals in fields such as industry, architecture, design, construction, and engineering.

Experience shows that drawing lessons organized on the basis of graphic assignments develop not only technical thinking but also the ability to find independent solutions in problem situations, propose new ideas, and make decisions using an engineering approach. In particular, lessons organized through modern pedagogical technologies—such as interactive

methods, problem-based learning, project-based learning, and the STEAM approach—activate students' thinking and enhance constructive thinking.

The didactic potential of technical drawing is also evident in its close connection with subjects such as mathematics, physics, technology, and informatics. This integration ensures interdisciplinary learning and connects students' knowledge with real-life experiences and technical processes. For example, the geometric shape of a part shown in a drawing is based on mathematical concepts, while its motion can be analyzed using physical laws. Thus, students engage with multiple disciplines simultaneously, which contributes to the comprehensive development of constructive thinking.

Today, the use of digital technologies in technical drawing lessons is expanding. Software such as AutoCAD, SolidWorks, and SketchUp enables students to model two- and three-dimensional objects, create real деталей, and produce technical drawings. These processes stimulate constructive thinking and help form a modern engineering culture in students. Through digital tools, students can create drawings not only on paper but also in virtual environments, preparing them for future technical professions.

Methodological approaches used in technical drawing lessons also play a crucial role in developing constructive thinking. Project-based tasks, graphic analysis exercises, problem-solving assignments, and independent drawing work help students develop graphic thinking, analyze object structures independently, and propose new solutions. In particular, tasks that require students to produce a technical solution, design a new component, or create a new form actively stimulate constructive thinking.

Research shows that drawing lessons aimed at developing constructive thinking enhance students' technical thinking levels, guide them toward technical professions, foster independent thinking, and encourage innovation. Especially through project-based tasks, students learn to improve existing objects, create new designs, or solve problems using graphical language. This develops not only knowledge and skills but also creativity and initiative.

In conclusion, technical drawing is not only a source of graphic knowledge but also an essential subject for developing technical thinking, spatial imagination, problem-solving abilities, graphic modeling skills, and most importantly, constructive thinking. The teacher's methodological approach, the use of technological tools, students' activity, and the complexity level of assignments all contribute to making this process more effective. Therefore, it is necessary to fully utilize the opportunities provided by technical drawing to shape students' thinking in a modern, technological, and creative way.

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